

Revising The Concept of Natural Numbers

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Abstract

Natural numbers, or whole numbers, understood abstractly as primarily numbers such as 3, 8, 5, 9, 12, and so on, are a fascinating concept. However, are they the only valid way of understanding and examining the concept of natural or whole numbers? The paper will attempt to revise natural numbers by removing their special formal status, as merely convenient and practical numbers representing amounts whole to themselves, emphasizing the concept that a number, representing an amount, is whole to itself. By examining the possibility of their revision as mere convenient numbers equal in formal value to other numbers as amounts representing themselves as wholes, the understanding of numbers and their values, both formal and informal, may be developed as an exercise in a combination of the properties of numbers and philosophical thought, a combination of elementary arithmetic as including the basic numbers, and of metaphysics regarding the nature of numbers in our reality.

Keywords

Mathematics, Arithmetic, Natural Numbers, Numbers, Philosophy of Mathematics

I. Introduction

Put abstractly, currently, natural numbers, also called whole numbers, are primarily understood as numbers such as 1, 5, 8, 12, 18, and so on. There are complex definitions and reasons for the current primary understanding, but regardless of such reasons, the end result is that numbers such as the aforementioned ones, are classified as natural numbers. However, this conceptual note will propose an alternative concept for natural numbers, presenting a different understanding to be utilized if so wished.

II. Revising Natural Numbers

What inherently makes a number such as 5 whole? Is it because it has no decimals? But what inherently makes a decimal not whole by itself? A number without decimals may be useful, but it is a number, it

represents an amount. So does a decimal, it is not contested that a number with decimals also represents an amount. But what inherently gives the number without decimals formal precedence, or the number with decimals formal subordination? A number is meant to represent an amount. If such is intended, then should a number not represent an individual valid amount by itself?

Is

4.238475748583757385 balls

Less valid than

4 balls

We can see that both are amounts represented as numbers. The reality in both situations is that there is a that amount of balls. 4 balls may be easier than 4.238475748583757385 balls, but does convenience override base logic in the base logic itself, rather than merely in practice? If there is an X amount of balls, then that is the amount of balls, that is the whole amount of balls there.

$X = X$

Even as fractions or as otherwise partial to another number, is it not still a definite amount, representing a whole number by itself? Regardless of relations to other numbers, as has been said, a number is an amount, an amount represents a whole amount by the virtue of being a representative of an amount, representing the whole amount of the amount.

As such, considering how numbers, at least primarily, represent amounts, that an amount is a whole amount of itself, could we not argue and possibly consider that perhaps there is no inherent whole number, because every number represents itself as a whole inherently, and as such, numbers such as 2, 4, 6, 8, and 10, should not have formal special status, but rather being convenient and practical amounts for usage, as lacking decimals to be inputted and calculated. We should at least consider this perspective, in comparison to the prevailing understandings for natural numbers.

Put concisely:

- If a number represents an amount.

- And a number is whole to itself.
- Then every number inherently represents itself as a whole.
- Therefore, the ontological status of current natural numbers becomes questionable due to having inherently the same wholeness relative to themselves.

Statements and Declarations

No funding was received for this paper, and the author declares no conflicts of interest.